

Synthesis of Fluorochalkones and Related Compounds. Part IV. Synthesis of $\beta\beta$ -Diphenylpropiophenones, "Dichalkones", and Related Quinquephenyl Derivatives

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Addition of benzene to fluorinated chalkones in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has been studied, yielding $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropiophenones. "Dichalkones" (*p*- and *m*-) have been synthesised and condensed with ethyl acetoacetate, yielding a number of related quinquephenyl derivatives.

$\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated carbonyl compounds, such as benzylideneacetophenone, alkylate aromatic rings to afford $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropiophenones¹ in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

This method has been applied in the present investigation to several fluorinated chalkones, reported earlier², for synthesis of a number of fluorinated $\beta\beta$ -diphenylpropiophenones (I).

A few quinquephenyl derivatives and their heterocyclic analogues, like quinquepyridyl and quinquethienyl are reported in literature³⁻⁵. Very recently, Davey and Maass⁶ have used the Michael reaction for synthesising such polyphenyls by the condensation of terephthalaldehyde or *m*-phthalaldehyde with acetophenone. In this communication, we also report the condensation of terephthalaldehyde and *m*-phthalaldehyde with various fluorinated acetophenones, viz., *p*-fluoroacetophenone⁷, 2-chloro-4-fluoro⁸, 3-methyl-4-fluoro⁹,

1. Blatt, "Organic Synthesis", Vol. II, 1967, John Wiley and Sons, Ltd.
2. Joshi and Jauhar, communicated to *Indian J. Chem.*
3. Burstallm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1962.
4. Steinkopf *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1941, 546, 180.
5. Sasse and Zschmeister, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 270.
6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4396.
7. Bui-Hoi and Kuong, *ibid.*, 1959, 386.
8. Bui-Hoi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, 2784.
9. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1798.

and 5-methyl-2-fluoro-acetophenones⁷, under the influence of saturated methanolic sodium hydroxide solution. This provided "*p*-dichalkones" (II) and "*m*-dichalkones" (III) in good yields.

(II)

(III)

These "dichalkones" were condensed with ethyl acetoacetate under conditions described by Nadkarni *et al.*⁹, when addition as well as cyclisation took place. Crystalline products were obtained in the case of the *p*-isomer, but the *m*-compounds always provided an oil. These dicarboxylate keto-esters (IV), when refluxed with aqueous ethanolic potassium hydroxide, underwent hydrolysis and simultaneous decarboxylation, giving rise to diketones (V).

(IV)

(V)

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Fluoro-, 2-chloro-4-fluoro-, 3-methyl-4-fluoro-, and 5-methyl-2-fluoro-acetophenones were obtained by following the methods of Buu-Hoi *et al.*¹⁰. Terephthalaldehyde and *m*-phthalaldehyde were prepared¹⁰ from *p*-xylene and *m*-xylene, respectively.

***ββ*-Diphenylpropiophenone.**—A mixture of benzene (42 ml) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.2*M*, 3.8 g.) was cooled in an ice-bath to 10° and maintained at 10–12° during addition of a solution of chalcone (0.58*M*, 4 g.) in benzene (10 ml). The reaction mixture was then stirred at the room temperature for about 2 hr. The yellow benzene solution was decanted to a mixture of HCl (dil.) and ice. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, and excess of benzene steam-distilled. The residual oil was cooled when it solidified to a brownish mass which was recrystallised from boiling ethanol with a pinch of animal charcoal. The compounds synthesised are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
Fluorinated *ββ*-diphenylpropiophenones (I).

Chalkones.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	
A. R' = 4'-fluoro.						
4,4'-DF	4-F	4'-F	80-81°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ OF ₂	C: 78.0% H: 4.5	78.2% 4.9
2'-Chloro-4,4'-DF	2-Cl-4F		63-64°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ OClF ₂	C: 70.1 H: 3.9	70.6 4.2
5'-Methyl-2',4'-DF	5-Me-2F		67°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ OF ₂	C: 78.4 H: 5.0	78.8 5.3
3'-Methyl-4,4'-DF	3-Me-4F		84-85°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ OF ₂	C: 78.4 H: 5.2	78.8 5.3
B. R' = 3', 4'-methylenedioxy.						
3,4-Methylenedioxy-4'-FC	4-F		94-95°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ F	C: 75.6 H: 4.7	75.8 4.8
2'-Chloro-3, 4-methylenedioxy-4'-FC	2-Cl-4-F		95°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ ClF	C: 69.0 H: 4.1	69.0 4.1
3,4-Methylenedioxy-3'-methyl-4'-FC	3-Me-4F		98-97°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ F	C: 76.1 H: 5.1	76.2 5.2

NB.—DF and FC denote respectively difluoro- and fluoro-chalkones.

Synthesis of "m-Dichalkone".—A saturated methanolic NaOH solution (0.5–1.0 ml) was added with stirring to a solution of *m*-phthalaldehyde (0.02*M*) and appropriate fluoroacetophenone (0.04*M*) in methanol (50 ml). The reaction mixture was left overnight; the solid separating was filtered and washed with cold and later with warm methanol.

Similar proportions of terephthalaldehyde and fluoroacetophenone were used in the preparation of "*p*-dichalkones", but instead of methanolic NaOH, a saturated methanolic

solution of KOH (0.5-1.0 ml) was used as the catalysing agent. The compounds synthesised are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

p-(or *m*)-Phenylenedi-(substituted phenylpropenones) ("dichalkones") (II & III).

Dichalkones.	R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>m</i> -Phenylenedi-(4-fluoro-PP)	4-F	4'-F	100-01°	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ F ₂	C: 76.9% H: 4.1	77.0% 4.2
<i>m</i> -Phenylenedi-(2-chloro-4-fluoro-PP)	2-Cl-4F	2'-Cl-4'-F	132°	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂	C: 64.0 H: 3.0	65.0 3.1
<i>m</i> -Phenylenedi-(2-fluoro-5-methyl-PP)	2-F-5-Me	2'-F-5'-Me	149-50°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ F ₂	C: 77.1 H: 4.8	77.6 4.9
<i>m</i> -Phenylenedi-(3-methyl-4-fluoro-PP)	3-Me-4-F	3'-Me-4'-F	134°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ F ₂	C: 77.2 H: 4.0	77.6 4.9
<i>p</i> -Phenylenedi-(4-fluoro-PP)	4-F	4'-F	213-14°	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ F ₂	C: 76.9 H: 4.3	77.0 4.2
<i>p</i> -Phenylenedi-(2-chloro-4-fluoro-PP)	2-Cl-4-F	2'-Cl-4'-F	176°	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂	C: 64.8 H: 3.3	65.0 3.1
<i>p</i> -Phenylenedi-(3-methyl-4-fluoro-PP)	3-Me-4-F	3'-Me-4'-F	101°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ F ₂	C: 77.4 H: 4.9	77.6 4.9

NB.—PP denotes phenylpropenone.

Addition of Ethyl Acetoacetate to "Dichalkones".—*p*-Dichalkone (0.006*M*) was added to a solution of sodium (0.006 g. atom) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.023*M*) in dry ethanol (100 ml). Refluxing for 2 hr. and cooling in an ice-salt mixture furnished the diethyl 6,6'-phenylenedi-(2-oxo-4-substituted phenylcyclohex-3-ene-carboxylate) (IV) which was recrystallised from ethanol (Table III).

TABLE III

Diethyl 0,6'-(*m* or *p*)-phenylenedi (2-oxo-4-substituted phenylcyclohex-3-ene-carboxylate) (IV).

Diethyl esters.	R = R ₁ .	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Requ.
6,6'- <i>m</i> -PD [2-oxo-4-(3'-methyl-4'-FP-C)]	3''-Me-4''-F	150°	C ₃₈ H ₃₆ O ₆ F ₂	C: 72.7 H: 5.5	72.8 5.7
6,6'- <i>p</i> -PD [2-oxo-4-(4'-FP-C)]	4''-F-4''-F	175°	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₆ F ₂	C: 72.1 H: 4.8	72.2 5.3
6,6'- <i>p</i> -PD [2-oxo-4-(3'-methyl-4'-FP)-C]	3''-Me-4''-F	168-69°	C ₃₈ H ₃₆ O ₆ F ₂	C: 72.6 H: 5.3	72.6 5.7

NB.—PD, FP and C denote respectively 'phenylenedi', 'fluorophenyl', and 'cyclohex-3-ene-carboxylate'.

In the case of "*m*-dichalkones", mostly oils were obtained; only diethyl 6,6'-*m*-phenylenedi-[2-oxo-4-(2''-methyl-4''-fluorophenyl)cyclohex-3-ene-carboxylate] was obtained in a crystalline form.

Hydrolysis of the Keto-ester.—The carboxylate ester (0.003*M*) was refluxed with aqueous ethanolic (4:1) KOH (0.6 g.) for 3 hr.. On dilution, 5,5'-*p*-phenylenedi-(3-substituted phenylcyclohex-2-en-one) (V) separating was recrystallised from dioxane.

The carboxylate derivatives of "m-dichalkones", which were obtained as oils, were also hydrolysed by ethanolic KOH. The solid diketones isolated were treated with warm HCl(dil.), washed with water, and recrystallised from dioxane. The compounds synthesised are listed in Table IV.

TABLE IV

5,5'-(*m*- or *p*)-Phenylenedi-(3-substituted phenylcyclohex-2-en-one) (V).

Cyclohexenones.	R=R'	M.P.	Formula	Found.	Reqd.
5,5'- <i>m</i> -PD [3(2'-chloro-4'-FP)-C']	2'-Cl-4'-F	95°	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₂ Cl ₂ F ₂	C: 70.0% H: 4.1	70.1% 4.2
5,5'- <i>m</i> -PD-[3(3'-methyl-4'-FP)-C']	3'-Me-4'-F	172°	C ₃₂ H ₄₈ O ₂ F ₂	C: 79.6 H: 5.7	79.6 5.8
5,5'- <i>m</i> -PD [3(5'-methyl-2'-FP)-C']	5'-Me-2'-F	Decomp.	C ₃₂ H ₄₈ O ₂ F ₂	C: 79.5 H: 5.5	79.6 5.6
5,5'- <i>p</i> -PD [3(4'-FP)-C']	4'-F	237°	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ O ₂ F ₂	C: 79.1 H: 5.2	79.2 5.2
5,5'- <i>p</i> -PD-[3(3'-methyl-4'-FP)-C']	3'-Me-4'-F	173°	C ₃₂ H ₄₈ O ₂ F ₂	C: 79.6 H: 5.6	79.6 5.6

N.B.—For "PD" and "FP" vide Table III. C' denotes "cyclohex-2-en-one"

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